

On the Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

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A variety of derivations of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution exist in the literature. For example, there is the original derivation by Maxwell in 1860 which uses symmetry arguments. Some books consider the number of combined states of many particles for a given energy E . A particle with energy e is then removed from the large system and one asks how many combined states exist when the total energy is now only $E-e$. [1] In addition, there are various factorial approaches which maximize the number of states related to constraints and there is also the approach of maximizing entropy given by the sum of $-\Pi \ln(\Pi)$ where Π is the probability for a state, also subject to constraints (which play a very important role in the final result). In addition, there is Boltzmann's transport equation [2] approach which considers single particle distribution functions and scattering. Some people [3] also consider taking a sum of variables and then applying the central limit theorem in order to obtain a Gaussian distribution of velocities. Finally, one can obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, by taking various limits of the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac quantum mechanical expressions, which start with the assumption that the weight for a many particle state of energy E and number of particles N is $\exp\{-(E-\mu N)/T\}$.

The objective of this note is to examine whether a different type of derivation follows from a consideration of differences in the scattering of fast particles versus slow ones. The objective is to try to see the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution result from the dynamics of colliding particles. Boltzmann has used scattering arguments, and his results allow for an equilibrium Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, but other solutions are also possible. The arguments presented here are of a "hand-waving" nature, but we think they are important because it would be good to have an understanding of equilibrium formation which does not rely on the idea of entropy or the number of states occupied. These are of course important ideas, but it seems that dynamics should drive the formation of equilibrium, not only for the scattering of particles, but in more general cases where the factor $\exp(-E/T)$ is used very freely.

Counting Energy States

First, let us examine one derivation for the Maxwell-Boltzmann equation [1] which focuses seriously on the counting of energy states. The following argument is presented on page 202.

$\ln W(E-e) = \ln[W(E)] - e \frac{d \ln W}{dE}$ with $\ln W/dE$ being defined as $1/kT$. T is the temperature and $W(E)$ represents the number of states of many particles with a total energy E .

Both sides are raised to exponential and one obtains $W(E-e)/W(e) = \exp(-e/kT)$ which is the Boltzmann distribution if e is replaced with the kinetic energy. It seems, however, that there may be a problem with this argument. $\ln[W(E)]$ is a large number, but in Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics e can approach infinity. The issue is that e/T must be very small compared with $\ln[W(E)]$ in order for the Taylor series to stop at the first expansion term. It is not at all clear that this is the case for large e . Another way to examine this issue is the following:

$$W(E-e) = W(E) - e \frac{dW}{dE} \quad \text{with } W(E) \gg e \frac{dW}{dE}.$$

If one divides by $W(E)$ then $1 \gg e/W \frac{dW}{dE} = e/T$ but e/T can be very large which contradicts this assumption.

Boltzmann Equilibrium Criterion

The powerful Boltzmann equilibrium condition is given by:

$$f(p_1)f(p_2) - f(p_3)f(p_4) \quad \text{where } p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4 \quad \text{and } K(p_1) + K(p_2) = K(p_3) + K(p_4)$$

Here p_1 to p_4 are momentum vectors and K is the kinetic energy. For the relativistic case, K can be replaced with E , the energy.

This criterion is based on scattering from p_1 and p_2 into p_3 and p_4 and guarantees equilibrium. One can immediately see that if $f(p) = \exp(-\text{quantity})$ where the "quantity" is conserved, one has a solution. Let us, however consider the scattering of a momentum p into $p+dp$.

Consider: $f(p)f(p_1) - f(p+dp)f(p_1')$ where we assume that p increases slightly. Then:

$$\frac{df/dp}{f(p)} = \frac{p}{p_1} \frac{df/dp(p_1)}{1/f(p_1)} \quad p_1'^2 = p_1^2 - 2p dp \quad \text{and } f(p) = B \exp(-Ap^2) \quad \text{where } A \text{ and } B \text{ are constants.}$$

The above calculation can be repeated using $K(p)$ instead of p as the variable. The results are the same.

For the relativistic case, using $e + e_1 = e + de + e_1 - de$ leads to $1/f \frac{df}{de} = \text{constant}$ where $e = \sqrt{p^2 + m^2}$. If one uses dp instead, one obtains $p/e \frac{d \ln f(p)}{dp} = -A$ where A is a constant. This leads to $f(p) = \exp\{-A \int e/p dp\}$ which in turn becomes $\exp(-B e)$ where B is another constant so the result is the same. Thus, solutions of the form $f(e) = \exp(-Ae)$ are obtained.

Thus, the Boltzmann equilibrium criterion does not give the exact form of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, but does give an exponential that drops as a function of energy. This is very important because the form of the Maxwell Boltzmann has been obtained strictly through an equilibrium balance equation and not using any statistics, maximization of entropy or counting of states.

We argue that there is nothing random or disorderly about the Boltzmann criterion. In fact, we argue the opposite. It is highly ordered, with balances ensuring constant $f(e)$'s and macroscopic changes give rise to very orderly sound waves.

The Boltzmann equilibrium criterion result is very interesting, but it is based on the scattering of two particles. The important point, however, seems to be that for the case of e (energy) changing from e to $e+de$, there is an equation which applies only to $f(e)$, namely $1/f df/de = \text{constant}$. This suggests that the important result $f(e) = \exp(-Ae)$ (which later becomes $\exp(-e/kT)$) is more general and can be applied to situations other than the scattering of two particles. A goal of this note is to see if this generalization can be found which allows one to immediately establish a relationship between $f(e)$ and $f(e+de)$.

Quantized Momentum States

Before attempting to find a more general reason for the relationship between $f(e)$ and $f(e+de)$, we briefly consider that effect of quantized momentum states. We assume that $f(e) = \exp(-e/kT)$. There is the appearance here of "a difficulty" in moving from one e state to a higher state, as the $f(e)$ drops. (This does not actually mean that such a transition is physically more difficult. This will be discussed later in the note.)

Consider a one dimensional well with quantized momentum levels given by $p = 2(3.14)n/L$ where n is an integer and L the length of the well. Now, let L approach infinity. This means the levels become very close and one is approaching the classical situation. Now, consider $f(e) = \exp(-e/kT)$. The difference in going from p to $p+dp$ gives $f(e+de) = f(e)(1-de/kT)$. It appears that one is making probability jumps of $1-de/kT$ as one jumps from one level to another. Thus, $1-de/kT$ measures the difficulty of a jump. Now $de = vdp$ (for a nonrelativistic situation), so the jump is becoming more and more difficult as energy increases. In other words, moving in steps of dp forces one to take larger and larger energy steps, which forces one to move to lower $f(p)$ values. This seems to suggest that the probability of transitioning from a high momentum p to $p+dp$ becomes more and more difficult. In calculations, however, de is thought of as a constant and this does not affect the calculation. It is good, however, to keep in mind that de is an increasing function with e .

As a next step, let us see attempt to see if there is a preferential direction to energy transfer when one has a fast moving particle in a dense gas of much slower particles.

Fast Particles versus Slow

Let us consider an example of a room at a party filled with people. Some are standing still, others are walking slowly, others a little faster. The room is densely filled and people are moving about, but the root mean square average speed is low and it represents a kind of temperature. Now, consider a person running into the room at a fast speed. This person will collide numerous times due to the high density and the trend will be for this person to lose energy. From the point

of view of energy alone, this person could draw energy from the party goes and increase his/her speed, but the probability of that happening is very low. The high probability is that the fast person loses his/her through many collisions.

We argue that the same happens for a very fast particle that is introduced into a dense gas in equilibrium at a low temperature T . This immediately raises the question why this is the case. Consider moving into the center of mass frame of the fast moving particle. Then, particles that were originally moving towards the particle in the lab frame are still approaching it, but any particle that was moving away with a lower velocity will now be seen to be approaching the fast particle. This implies that the fast particle will undergo many collisions with the slow particles. The next question is whether these collisions give or draw energy from the fast particle. To attempt to answer this question, consider a fast and a slow particle hitting a strong wall. It is possible for both of them to bounce back with the same momentum with which they struck. If the wall is weak, however, the slow particle may be the only one to bounce back. The fast particle may do work changing the wall (i.e. crushing part of it etc). It is argued that in a dense gas, the fast particle tends to push other particles aside, thus doing work and losing energy. A slow particle on the other hand has more of a tendency to bounce back, thus retaining its energy. For example, the nonelastic case of a slow particle and a fast particle hitting a somewhat large mass shows that the slow particle can bounce back, whereas the fast particle may have enough energy to actually push the mass. This leads to a loss of energy of the fast particle.

Let us consider the case of a slow particle which happens to hit a fast particle. It can transfer energy to the fast particle. In the center of mass frame of the slow particle, however, only fast particles which were approaching the slow particle in the lab frame will still be approaching and will possibly lead to collisions. Thus, there will be fewer collisions. We argue that there is an important idea occurring, namely that high energy particles are more "unstable" than lower energy ones, in terms of the retention of their kinetic energy. This could be important because $f(e)$ density might decrease as e increases, due to the instability of the higher energy particles retaining their kinetic energy.

Non-Scattering View of the Boltzmann Equilibrium Criterion

As shown above, the Boltzmann equilibrium criterion leads to $1/f \, df/de = A$ where A is a constant. This is interesting because one originally started with two colliding particles. The end result, however, holds for one, i.e. one does not even need to think of colliding particles. The objective of this section is to see if the expression $f(e) = \exp(-Ade)$ can be obtained in a general manner, without counting states or maximizing entropy. If so, this factor could be used in many situations (e.g. the canonical distribution, grand canonical etc).

It is argued that there are a number of collisions leading from e to $e+de$ and time reversal allows for the reverse collisions to occur. It is also argued that the a higher momentum (or energy) particle has a higher probability of "shedding" its energy. Thus, going from $f(e)$ to $f(e+de)$, there is drop in f because the higher energy particles tend to "shed" their energy. Thus, there is no paradox as described by a quote from [4] which states: "Baierlein has written: 'Qualitatively stated, the probability of high energy states is exponentially smaller than the

probability of low-energy states". The converse must follow; the probability of low-energy states is exponentially higher than the probability of high-energy states. Therefore the most probable state is $E_i=0$, regardless of temperature..."

There is no need to assume an inherent decrease in probability going from e to $e+de$, rather the particles with $e+de$ shed their energy very quickly making their count small and thus their probability small. A decrease in probability going from $f(e)$ to $f(e+de)$ does, however, give the "appearance" of a "barrier" or "hindrance". It "appears" as if it is more difficult to go from e to $e+de$. Thus, one should also be able to develop an argument along these lines as well:

$f(e+de)-f(e) = -f(e)B$ where B is the small probability of going to a higher energy, such as a probability given by a Poisson distribution. B is not a function of energy because many collisions can potentially lead to e changing from $e+de$ regardless of e . Even if de increases as $2pdp$ (or the nonrelativistic case), $2pdp$ is still an infinitesimal amount.

Then: $de \frac{df}{de} = -f B$ and $B/de = A$ a constant because both B and de are tiny. This will again lead to the result: $f(e)=\exp(-Ae)$ which should hold in relativistic and nonrelativistic cases. The main point, however, is there is only the appearance of a physical hindrance moving from e to $e+de$. Physically, the tendency of high energy particles to quickly "decay" or "shed their energy" may account for the lower probability of $f(e+de)$ as compared to $f(e)$. Here it should be noted that "high energy" is relative to an average energy or temperature.

Thus, it may be possible to obtain the Boltzmann equilibrium criterion result $\exp(-Ae)$ without any scattering picture or any counting of states or maximization of entropy expressions.

Conclusion:

The conclusion of this note is that the statistical factor $\exp(-e/T)$, or at least $\exp(-Ae)$, appears very naturally from Boltzmann's equilibrium criterion $f(e_1)f(e_2)-f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and holds in both relativistic and nonrelativistic cases. If one lets $e_1=e$ and $e_2=e+de$, one is able to obtain an equation for $f(e)$ alone, namely $1/f \frac{df}{de}=-A$ where A is constant. This leads to an $\exp(-eA)$ factor and suggests that this factor may arise in more general cases than just the collisions of two particles. The physical picture put forward is one of the "appearance" of an increasing difficulty of obtaining high energy states. Ultimately, however, it seems that the high "decay" rate of high energy or momentum particles may be the cause of $f(e+de)$ being smaller than $f(e)$. We argue that high energy particles tend to smash into nearby particles doing work and losing their energy and so have a higher tendency of "decaying" or "shedding energy" than lower energy particles. Here it should be noted that "high energy" is relative to an average energy or temperature. We argue that this is the dynamical reason for a decrease in $f(e)$. Such a dynamical picture does not depend on counting states or the idea of entropy. This is not to say that these are not "in the picture", but rather suggests that there should be a dynamical driver of equilibrium. We argue that it is important to have a physical picture based on dynamics to describe the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, and ultimately the factor $\exp(-E/T)$ which is used throughout statistical mechanics.

References:

- [1] Reif F., Fundamentals of Statistical and Thermal Physics. New York: McGraw Hill, 1965.
- [2] Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics 2nd Edition. New York: John Wiley, 1963.
- [3] Sands, D. and Dunning-Davies, J. The Canonical Distribution and Central Limit Theorem.
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